

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

Initial Communication Plan

KNAW-NIOD, PIN

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Author(s)
Reto Speck
Stefano Sbarbati
Sheena Bassett
Franco Niccolucci
Petra Drenth

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Author(s)	Reto Speck, KNAW-NIOD Stefano Sbarbati, PIN Sheena Bassett, PIN Franco Niccolucci, PIN Petra Drenth, KNAW-NIOD
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1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the initial results of PARTHENOS WP8 “Communication, dissemination and outreach”, task 2 “Development and update of a coordinated communication plan”. It provides a general communication and dissemination strategy for PARTHENOS, as well as a detailed plan of action for months 1 to 15 of the project.

The plan is a live document and it will be updated at months 15, 27, 39 and 48. Updates will contain an evaluation of the communication activities undertaken during the previous period; an updated version of the general communication strategy; and detailed planning for the period ahead

The general objectives of PARTHENOS WP8 are to:

- disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes,
- set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, professionals, decisions makers, public, etc.),
- exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations.

The present document acts as a general roadmap for all PARTHENOS-related communication and dissemination activities. It presents PARTHENOS’ overall communication and dissemination strategy (sections 3 and 5); analyses the project’s stakeholder communities (section 4); presents a set of core communication messages (section 6); analyses the communication resources available to the project (section 7); describes the project’s own communication channels (section 8) and dissemination materials produced by the project (section 9); lists external dissemination opportunities (section 10), and sets evaluation targets for the first 12 months (section 11).

2 Introduction and background

PARTHENOS is a project funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 framework programme that started on the 1st May 2015. The project life span is four years. The consortium built around PARTHENOS is composed of fifteen partners from nine countries. It includes the two European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) active in the broad fields of the humanities – DARIAH and CLARIN – as well as five major European research infrastructure projects – ARIADNE, CENDARI, CHARISMA/IPERION-CH, EHRI, DCH-RP.

The overall goals of PARTHENOS are to:

- increase the cohesion of research sectors in the field of Linguistic Studies, Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and related fields;
- define and implement common guidelines and best practices enabling cross-discipline data curation policies;
- establish a vision about shared virtual research methods for humanities supported by foresight studies;
- mainstream standardization and interoperability in order to support data sharing and re-use ;
- develop common tools for data oriented services.

If these objectives are to be achieved during the lifetime of the project, a co-ordinated and comprehensive set of dissemination and communication activities are required in order to maximise the impact of the project both within the consortium and on its external stakeholders.

Work package (WP) 8 is charged with planning, co-ordinating and implementing all of the project's communication and dissemination activities. The WP consists of six tasks:

Task 8.1 – Project web site and portal: This task concerns the creation of the PARTHENOS website, which is defined as the central hub of all the project's external

communication activities. Details about the initial design and implementation of the project website can be found in section 8.1.

Task 8.2 – Development and update of a coordinated communication plan: The present document and its future iterations are developed within this task.

Task 8.3 – Scientific communication: This task concerns communication at the scientific level. It will evaluate the creation of a scientific e-journal in the service of e-humanities research, and the creation and operation of an open access repository.

Task 8.4 – Organization of joint events: This task concerns the organisation of joint events (symposia, workshops, public presentations) directly managed by the project, possibly co-located at other international/national events and in collaboration with other major national and international projects.

Task 8.5 – Liaisons with other international initiatives: This task aims at coordinating and pooling existing networks external to the consortium in order to realise mutual benefits.

Task 8.6 – Publicity and outreach: This task concerns activities and materials aimed at informing the public at large of the project's plans and works. The task co-ordinates and plans outreach opportunities (press conferences, interviews, newspaper articles, etc.), and the preparation of high-quality publicity materials.

The present document was prepared in T8.2. It presents PARTHENOS' overall communication and dissemination strategy (sections 3 and 5); analyses the project's stakeholder communities (section 4); presents a set of core communication messages (section 6); analyses the communication resources available to the project (section 7); describes the project's own communication channels (section 8) and dissemination materials produced by the project (section 9); lists external dissemination opportunities (section 10), and sets evaluation targets for the first 12 months (section 11).

3 Communication and dissemination strategy

3.1 Overall objectives

The overall objectives of PARTHENOS' communication and dissemination activities are to

- disseminate effectively the project goals and outcomes,
- set up efficient tools for the communication towards various stakeholders (scientific communities, professionals, decisions makers, public, etc.),
- exploit synergies in liaisons and collaborations.

In order to reach these general objectives, five specific objectives have been identified:

- identify and involve internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
- create an affiliate network of external stakeholders (research infrastructures and networks in related fields);
- ensure that PARTHENOS reaches the core scientific communities in linguistic studies, digital humanities, digital heritage, archaeology and history, as well as professionals in related fields;
- raise awareness about PARTHENOS amongst policy makers, funding bodies and major related public institutions;
- devise a strategy to involve the general public and attract non-professional audiences.

3.2 SWOT analysis

The mission of the PARTHENOS, the context in which it operates, and the composition of its consortium lead to a number of unique strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in regard to its communication and dissemination objectives. These unique characteristics are analysed in Table 1 as follows:

Strengths (helpful & internal)	Weaknesses (harmful & internal)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• experienced management and sufficient resources• involvement of experienced professionals• project's unique approach• project's long term vision• consortium encompasses a large network of stakeholders including existing Research Infrastructures, possessing strong established dissemination channels• high level of freedom	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• consortium's large size and diversity• tailoring messages to diverse audiences may be difficult• news worthiness• difficulty in reaching audiences beyond academia such as policy makers, the general public.• difficulty in framing (horizontally vs vertically) our communication• lack of involvement, unresponsive partners
Opportunities (helpful & external)	Threats (harmful & external)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• spin news values in our favour (e.g. the message "investing in culture is investing in future")• involvement of truly international actors• possibility to create "something different" from scratch• reaching out to less well represented countries such as newer member states• present and justify investment in research to the public	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• academic approach to media attention• bureaucracy• (too) specific and jargon based information• lack of co-ordination, leading to message "silos" rather than a single coherent message• "flat" news feed; failure to continuously keep stakeholders informed.

Table 1: SWOT Analysis

Our SWOT analysis indicates that PARTHENOS has a unique opportunity to reach a very wide and varied audience to disseminate information about the project's innovative research, and to promote the societal and cultural value of humanities research across

European societies. However, the project will only be able to realise this potential if it can efficiently marshal the existing communication and dissemination networks and resources already in existence among its partner institutions and affiliated projects, and if it manages to frame its messages in a coherent, well co-ordinated manner and in accordance to the needs of its various stakeholder communities.

3.3 Communication and dissemination principles

This section presents a set of five basic principles that have informed the articulation of the PARTHENOS Communication Plan. Adherence to these principles will ensure that the project can fully exploit its strengths and opportunities, while diminishing and managing its weakness and threats as outlined above.

1. **Adaptability.** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication strategy needs to be comprehensive enough to cover the project as a whole, while being adaptable to the project's various research themes and stakeholder communities. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users.
2. **Flexibility.** As per the previous pillar, PARTHENOS' communication needs to be flexible and open, in order to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
3. **Dynamism.** The dynamic element is the natural consequence of the two points above. A dynamic strategy is a key to maximise the impact of PARTHENOS.
4. **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** As stated above, PARTHENOS needs to be able to speak to academic audiences in a variety of fields, as well as to decision makers and the public at large. To achieve this, PARTHENOS will follow a multi-layered communication strategy that formulates core messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication).
5. **Exploitation of synergies:** PARTHENOS is a clustering project across existing Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives and e-infrastructures in the fields of Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Linguistic Studies, Archaeology and related fields. As such, the project can draw upon a plethora of expertise, networks

and dissemination and communication channels that are already in existence at partner institutions and related projects and that can reach the specific subject communities with which PARTHENOS wishes to engage. PARTHENOS needs to exploit to the fullest the synergy that can be achieved by building bridges between these existing resources, and must avoid a duplication of effort. Therefore, achieving better co-ordination and cross-fertilisation of existing communication and dissemination activities is central to PARTHENOS' mission.

4 Stakeholder communities

Key to a successful attainment of PARTHENOS' communication and dissemination goals is a throughout understanding of the key stakeholder communities with which the project needs to engage. This section identifies and presents the different stakeholder communities relevant to PARTHENOS.

The impact PARTHENOS will have on these communities varies considerably, and the influence each community can exert on the project is equally diverse. Moreover, each community has distinct needs and interests in terms of communication. Therefore, it is essential that PARTHENOS develops a thorough understanding of its stakeholder communities in order to be able to hone and target its communication and dissemination activities accordingly; to develop appropriate channels for contacting and informing stakeholder groups; and to design and plan dissemination materials and activities that maximize the visibility and impact of the project.

The PARTHENOS stakeholder communities are:

- Internal stakeholders, i.e. institutional partners who are part of PARTHENOS' consortium and projects associated to the project;
- Research institutions, international networks and individual researchers at varying career levels (PhDs, post-docs/early career researchers, senior researchers) active in the subject areas covered by PARTHENOS;
- Galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAMs) operating in these fields
- Non-academic professionals working in fields related to PARTHENOS' activities such as data management, the cultural industries, etc.
- Educators and students at varying levels in the subject areas covered by PARTHENOS;
- Relevant politicians, policy makers and funding bodies;
- The media and the general public.

Figure 1 attempts to visualise the degree of influence and mutual dependence that exists between these stakeholder communities on the one hand, and the project on the other. It should be noted, however, that the boundaries, represented as concentric circles in the diagram, are indicative rather than categorical. They merely exist to highlight the heterogeneous nature of the PARTHENOS' stakeholders, and to emphasise the need for a tailored approach to communication and dissemination, rather than act as a prescriptive classification.

Figure 1: Stakeholder map

Table 2 provides an in-depth analysis of each stakeholder communities' importance and interests, communication and dissemination requirements, and an indication of the channels we will employ to reach them.

Stakeholder group	Description and examples	Interested in PARTHENOS' news about:	Importance	To be reached through the following channels:
Internal - institutional partners - associated projects	Managers, decisions makers and researchers at partner institutions and associated projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Development of the shared infrastructure - Details about innovations and new tools and methods - Best practice, guidelines and training opportunities - Conferences and other PARTHENOS events 	Very high partners need to be fully engaged in order to get their full support for the project, and to spread news about PARTHENOS' via their own networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Internal meetings - PARTHENOS conferences/events - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.) - Newsletters (internal/external) - Publications

<p>Researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -international networks - institutions - individuals (at all career levels) 	<p>The communities of researchers, networks and institutions active in the PARTHENOS subject areas of digital humanities, digital heritage, linguistic studies, archaeology and history</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to data and resources - Recent developments in relevant RIs - Forthcoming events, workshops and training opportunities - Details about innovations and access to new tools and methods - Details about how PARTHENOS will innovate research 	<p>Very high – the principal subject communities underlying PARTHENOS and its associated RIs need to be convinced that PARTHENOS will enhance their research activities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Publications - Conference presentations - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.) - Direct networking and via partners'/associated projects' dissemination channels
<p>GLAMs/Professionals</p>	<p>GLAMs active in the subject areas covered by PARTHENOS; non-academic professional working in fields such as data/information management or the cultural industries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview about PARTHENOS' mission and its progress - Details about innovations and access to new tools and methods - Best practice guidelines 	<p>Medium to high: outreach beyond academia is highly desirable; GLAMs as important providers of data and expertise to RIs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Publications - Press releases - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.)

Educators/Students	Educators and students at varying levels in the subject areas covered by PARTHENOS.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview about PARTHENOS' mission and its progress - Examples of how PARTHENOS will innovate research in the various subject areas. 	Medium: desirable to reach, and contribute to the education of, the next generation of researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website/social media - Newsletter (external) - Press releases - Publicity material (flyers, short videos, etc.)
Politicians, policy makers and funders	All the institutional or individual actors that frame the wider context of (European) humanities research/RI development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview about PARTHENOS' mission and its progress - Innovation potential of PARTHENOS, and benefits the project offers to stakeholders and end-users - Socio-economic impact of PARTHENOS. 	High: their support is needed to ensure the long-term future of PARTHENOS and its outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct networking - Policy briefing - Press releases
Media/general public	Media outlets and individuals with an interest in RIs/research in the subject areas covered by PARTHENOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview about PARTHENOS' mission and its progress - Benefits, including socio-economic impact, of PARTHENOS' achievements 	Media: outreach beyond academia is very important: demonstrate benefits of public investment into research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Press releases/media coverage - Website/social networks

Table 2: Stakeholder analysis

5 Multi-level communication

One of the main challenges for PARTHENOS is to talk appropriately to all of its stakeholder communities. This implies that PARTHENOS needs to support communication and dissemination activities that are detailed and technical to satisfy the needs of professional and research communities; broad, strategic and clear to have an impact on policy makers and funding bodies; and plain, general and “jargon-free” in order to attract the attention of the interested public.

This challenge manifests itself most prominently in regard to those communication channels – especially the website, social media and press releases – that target all the project’s stakeholder communities indiscriminately. One should not underestimate the extent of the challenge. Indeed, given that most PARTHENOS partners’ expertise lies in (academic) research, there is a clear danger of defaulting to an academic style of communication, even if this style is not the best suited for a given communication channel and/or to reach a given target audience.

Such a defaulting would entail the risk of losing the interest of important stakeholders. It would also result in the project’s dissemination and communication efforts aligning poorly to the European Commission's strategy in the field of communication of joint European research results, which places a special emphasis on reaching non-academic audiences – see, for instance:

- European Commission (2004), *European Research - A guide to successful communications*. EU Publications Office, Luxembourg.
- European Commission (2008). *Scientific evidence for policymaking*. Publications Office, Luxembourg.
- European Commission (2010). *Communicating research for evidence-based policymaking. A practical guide for researchers in socio-economic sciences and humanities*. Publications Office, Luxembourg.

In order to tackle this issue, we will design the website and other generic communication instruments in such a way that it can encompass differing styles of communication.

In fact, as further described in section **Error! Reference source not found.**, the project website will not only be used as a focal point for all PARTHENOS-related dissemination activities, but also as a news hub about research, digital humanities, innovation and technology in general. Both sections will live simultaneously on the website.

While the focus will always be on reporting and disseminating the project's activities, the "news hub" will foster the publicity of those activities using the following communicational frame:

Investing in culture is investing in the future

This will help to frame PARTHENOS's research mission in a way that is interesting enough to compete in today's noisy communication environment, while also helping the project to reach a general audience. Thereby, we hope to disseminate the achievements of PARTHENOS as relevant and meaningful to communities beyond academia.

To achieve this goal, our communication strategy needs to develop along three trajectories:

- Communication aimed at internal stakeholders, researchers, educators and non-academic professionals.
- Communication aimed at the media and the general public.
- Communication aimed at policy and decision makers and funding bodies.

While the requirements to successfully communicate to the first group are relatively clear and well understood, a few more words about the other two trajectories are in order.

The second trajectory aims to engage and address general audiences. This category is broad enough to include specialised media, national and local institutions and the interested public. In order to create interest around PARTHENOS among these communities, we need to focus on the following:

- Compelling visual style (website, multimedia production and materials need to be designed with this specific segments in mind – e.g. fresh, appealing and easy to use appearance);
- Effective story telling. We need to create stories that are interesting for the public, by, for instance, referring to the “investing in research/culture is investing in the future” interpretative framework;
- PARTHENOS website as an hub for the information related to Cultural Heritage, Digital Humanities and Technologies;
- Other media channels as appropriate e.g. YouTube.

Regarding policy-, decision-makers and funding bodies, an EC paper of 2008 entitled “*Scientific evidence for policymaking*” provides some useful pointers of how to target these groups. The paper advises project’s to develop “appropriate dissemination and knowledge sharing strategies from the earliest stages of project planning; include partners from the world of policy-making in their project team in order to ensure that the subjects chosen, as well as the scope of the research, respond to defined policymaking priority areas¹”. Moreover, the paper recommends to “develop more subtle ways of engaging with the broader public and embedding social and ethical reflection within the everyday practice of science, develop a programme and a methodology of dissemination of results over the lifecycle of their project in order to provide updated information on progress over time; reflect in terms of added-value of the work undertaken, not only in terms of the scientific research, but in terms of the policy-usefulness of the work undertaken; prepare policy briefings which are easily readable, understandable and useable by policymakers in framing and/or evaluating policies²”

In other words, the third trajectory of PARTHENOS’ communication strategy combines elements from the other two. Specific actions and tailored messages targeting policy makers need to be defined on a case by case basis.

¹ European Commission (2008). *Scientific evidence for policymaking*. Publications Office, Luxembourg, p. 9

² *Ibid.*, p. 10-11

6 Tailored messages

This section presents a set of tailored messages aimed at different communities that should help to hone the project's communication along the three trajectories detailed in section **Error! Reference source not found.** above. The following messages have been developed:

- General message
- Extended general message
- Research and educational message
- Jargon-free public message
- Policy- and decision-maker message

It should be noted that these messages are indicative rather than prescriptive. Indeed, partners are encouraged to adapt these messages according to their needs. Particularly, the "Research and educational message" may need adapting depending on the specific subject community that is being addressed.

6.1 General message

This represents the **official definition** of the project, displayed on the project's website, and will also be used on official dissemination materials.

PARTHENOS aims at strengthening the cohesion of research in the broad sector of Linguistic Studies, Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and related fields through a thematic cluster of European Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives and infrastructures, and building bridges between different, although tightly, interrelated fields. PARTHENOS will achieve this objective through the definition and support of common standards, the coordination of joint activities, the harmonization of policy definition and implementation, and the development of pooled services and of shared solutions to the same problems.

6.2 Extended general message

The description above, while very complete and exhausting, can be integrated with other information regarding the scope of the project and the composition of the consortium. The following is the extended description of the project, to be mainly used for communication activities directed to specific stakeholders' groups.

PARTHENOS aims at strengthening the cohesion of research in the broad sector of Linguistic Studies, Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and related fields through a thematic cluster of European Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives, e-infrastructures and other world-class infrastructures, and building bridges between different, although tightly, interrelated fields. PARTHENOS will achieve this objective through the definition and support of common standards, the coordination of joint activities, the harmonization of policy definition and implementation, and the development of pooled services and of shared solutions to the same problems.

PARTHENOS will address and provide common solutions to the definition and implementation of joint policies and solutions for the humanities and linguistic data lifecycle, taking into account the specific needs of the sector that require dedicated design, including provisions for cross-discipline data use and re-use, the implementation of common AAA (authentication, authorization, access) and data curation policies, including long-term preservation; quality criteria and data approval/certification; IPR management, also addressing sensitive data and privacy issues; foresight studies about innovative methods for the humanities; standardization and interoperability; common tools for data-oriented services such as resource discovery, search services, quality assessment of metadata, annotation of sources; communication activities; and joint training activities. Built around the two ERICs of the sector, DARIAH and CLARIN, and involving all the relevant Integrating Activities projects, PARTHENOS will deliver guidelines, standards, methods, services and tools to be used by its partners and by all the research community. It will exploit commonalities and synergies to optimize the use of resources in related domains.

6.3 Research and educational message

This message aims to highlight the advantages that the research and educational sectors can gain through PARTHENOS. It focuses on data use and re-use, a topical issue in

today's research area, and on the impetus to professional development and advancement that PARTHENOS provides.

It is important to note that, given the heterogeneity of the consortium, tailored messages that reflect partners' specific area(s) of interests should be created. This will help to maximise the impact in the various research communities addressed by the project, while also helping the consortium to keep control over the global message.

Keywords: research infrastructures; involvement of researchers; benefits for researchers; data management; data use/re-use; intellectual property rights; tools and services; standards and guidelines; training; open access; integration and pooling of data, service and expertise.

Digital technologies have so far created large digital archives, and new methodologies to support research. It is now necessary to integrate these archives and support these new methods. This is the mission of newly set-up pan-European bodies, called European research infrastructures, created to provide integrated and coordinated facilities, resources and related services to the scientific community to conduct top-level research in their respective fields. PARTHENOS is going to support the work of the two research infrastructures of our sector, called CLARIN (language studies) and DARIAH (digital humanities), as well as the contributions of various integration projects addressing specific subdomains. By pooling efforts, taking advantage of commonalities among the involved disciplines, and collecting indications from the respective research communities, results in terms of services and tools will be better, and closer to researchers' needs.

Individual researchers are now able to benefit of the advanced services made available to everybody by PARTHENOS, and may have a voice in the project development by letting the project know their needs and wishes. Such services concern all aspects of data management, including: access to and sharing of data; management of intellectual property rights; integration of diverse datasets through shared understanding of concepts and content typical of the various disciplines and approaches; tools for discovering openly available resources such as archives, services and tools; guidelines for making the best use of digital technologies; and, finally, training on all of the above. Sharing research outcomes in an open access

repository of scientific papers is an important component of this strategy. PARTHENOS fosters the participation of all researchers in its activities and welcomes the involvement and participation of all research institutions, to enlarge the network of facilities, resources and services integrated in the research infrastructures it is serving.

Similarly, the high rate of innovation in PARTHENOS is the key to present the project to educators and students.

Keywords: innovation; involvement of education communities; training of young researchers; development of innovative curricula.

Education must not be left behind the advances in research methodology, to prepare tomorrow's researchers and professionals. Basing on the experience of its partners that are primary educational institutions, PARTHENOS addresses innovation in training and education with a specific activity, developing training plans and up-to-date curricula. Participation and involvement of all actors from the education domain is welcome to collect requirements, test proposals and verify solutions. In return, educators will receive detailed information about current educational offerings for digital humanities and well-designed plans and curricula they can adapt and implement according to their needs and educational offerings.

6.4 Jargon-free public message

The following message targets the general public. Despite being a pure research project, PARTHENOS needs to find compelling ways to target this audience.

Keywords: social and economic relevance of culture/research; “investing in culture is investing in the future”; value for money; new digital tools and methods to explore culture.

Culture shapes our identities, aspirations and relations to others and the world. It also shapes the places and landscapes where we live, the lifestyles we develop. Arts, heritage, history, literature and language are essential components of our European identity as well as key factors of social and economic development. Investing in culture is investing in the future. Continuously improving our understanding of history, literature, language, arts and heritage, by availing of innovative communication and

information technologies that nowadays are part of our everyday life is a necessity, and pooling resources at European level will save money, avoid duplication or – even worst – divergence of efforts, and optimize results.

The European Commission provides significant support to research in the cultural domain, and PARTHENOS is a beneficiary of the EC's "positive spending review" that has resulted in a bolstering of the budget of Horizon 2020, the main European research programme.

PARTHENOS will ensure value for money by improving research work in the cultural domain, by providing better and more efficient digital services and tools that are based on information technology, and by ensuring the exploitation of the wealth of information that is already digitally available. Updating the methodologies used in the cultural domains will make cultural content more familiar and accessible to everybody, will help the discovery of new significance in old concepts, and will eventually contribute to social and economic development, thereby resulting in growth and jobs in a strategic sector for Europe.

6.5 Policy- and decision-maker message

As with the public message, the core theme for the message targeted at policy- and decision-makers is "Investing in culture is investing in the future".

Keywords: social and economic relevance of research infrastructures; job creation.

PARTHENOS and the Europe-wide research infrastructures it supports will not only benefit research, cultural and educational institutions, but also the public at large. Improved knowledge in the cultural domain will lead to significant social and economic benefits, not least by accelerating growth and creating jobs in a strategic sector for Europe. The strong commitment to research infrastructures provided by the European Commission in the Horizon 2020 Programme, needs to be accompanied by concrete and operational support to national and local initiatives participating in this trans-national and interdisciplinary effort.

A similar message should be addressed to practitioners, professionals and GLAMs, adding, "As it happened in the past for other technologies (photography is a ready example), research methods impact directly on professional practice, both of individuals

and of institutions. That is why cultural institutions such as archives, libraries, museums and heritage agencies, as well as professionals operating in these field, must be tightly connected to important developments such as the creation of Europe-wide research infrastructures: research infrastructures will assist cultural institutions to achieve their missions in the service of European culture, and will receive important indications on the social implications of their research work.”

7 Available resources

The aim of this section is to identify the relevant communication and dissemination skills, resources and networks available within the project consortium.

7.1 Consultation of the PARTHENOS partners

Two surveys launched by PIN in the first two months of the project have contributed much of the information presented in this section as well as in sections 8 and 9. These surveys are:

1. Survey of planned dissemination activities and existing communication channels.

This survey is implemented as a google spreadsheet (<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jMfPD5VxL8lrIUaMj1fr08NkuQxRoLjL-qfQQYjT2pk/edit#gid=0>). In order to ensure the consistency and comparability of gathered data, several categories and data validation rules are hard coded into the spread sheet.

All partners have been invited to input relevant information about the following directly into the spreadsheet:

- Planned/Forthcoming PARTHENOS-related events;
- Planned/forthcoming PARTHENOS-related publications;
- Established dissemination channels (such as journals, newsletters, publications, website, social media, etc.);
- Undertaken/planned networking/other activities (such as PARTHENOS-related presentations; PARTHENOS-related contributions to Newsletters, blogs, etc.).

This survey will remain open throughout the duration of the project, and partners are asked to update their information regularly. This way, the spreadsheet will become an important record of dissemination activities undertaken by the project, as well as constitute a valuable planning and working tool that contains up-to-date details about forthcoming dissemination opportunities and about existing channels that can be exploited by PARTHENOS.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Partner name	Start Date	End Date	Location	Title	Description	Organized by	Target Groups	People re
2	All partners	01/07/2015	02/07/2015	Florence, Italy	PARTHENOS Kick-off Meeting	First plenary of PARTHENOS Projec PIN Scrl		Project Partners	
3	Partners of WP5&6	09/06/2015	11/06/2015	Heraklion, Greec	WP5 and WP6 Pre-kick-off Meeting	Preparation and Planning of WP5 ar	FORTH & CNR	Partners of WP5 and WP6	
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Figure 2 Survey of planned dissemination activities and existing communication channels

2. Survey of partners’ communication goals and feedback on PARTHENOS’ communication strategy

The aim of the survey is to collect qualified opinions and qualitative data from partners to shape the PARTHENOS’ communication strategy according to the partners’ needs and opinions.

The survey is implemented as an online Typeform survey, and it accessible at <https://stefanosbarbati.typeform.com/to/umoZzH>

The survey is composed of twelve questions, arranged around three main survey areas:

- Identification and description of the main communication goal of each partner (independently from PARTHENOS),
- Identification of the main communication goal of each partner within PARTHENOS project,
- Measuring the level of agreement and disagreement to the general communication approach proposed.

9 → How much do you agree with the following statement:*

PARTHENOS' website should be focused **only** on project-related activities and achievements

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Not at all Very much

10 → How much do you agree with the following statement:*

PARTHENOS' website should include **also** news and features other than the pure project-related ones

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Not at all Very much

11 → How much do you agree with the following statement:*

PARTHENOS' website should be designed to attract mostly Educators/Students

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Figure 3 Survey of partners' communication goals and feedback on PARTHENOS' communication strategy

While the survey is currently still open, preliminary results suggests that partners generally agree with the multi-level and multi-stakeholder communication strategy described above.

7.2 Resources available in the consortium

WP8 is led by KNAW-NIOD and involves all partners in the consortium. Most partners have public relations departments in their institutions and access to existing communication and dissemination networks and resources which should be exploited to disseminate PARTHENOS.

The following table gives an overview of the partners' responsibilities and contributions to the main communication and dissemination tasks.

Task No.	Task	Responsibilities	Main contact
	Overall co-ordination of communication/dissemination activities	KNAW-NIOD (WPL), supported by PIN (Coordinator)	Reto Speck reto.speck@kcl.ac.uk
T8.1.	Design, development and technical maintenance of website	PIN, supported by KNAW-NIOD	Stefano Sbarbati stefano.sbarbati@pin.unifi.it
T8.1/8.6	Sharing project-internal news through the project website/social media	PIN, supported by KNAW-NIOD. Input from all partners	Stefano Sbarbati stefano.sbarbati@pin.unifi.it
T8.1/8.6	Sharing relevant external news (i.e. news from partners, associated projects, etc.) through the project website/social media	KNAW-NIOD, supported by PIN. Input from all partners	Petra Drenth P.Drenth@niod.knaw.nl
T8.2	Periodic update of coordinated communication plan	KNAW-NIOD, supported by PIN, CSIC and MIBACT-ICCU. Input from all partners	Reto Speck reto.speck@kcl.ac.uk
T8.3	Evaluation/potential implementation of a scientific e-journal	UGOE, supported by KNAW, CNRS, CSIC and KCL	Juliane Stiller stiller@fh-potsdam.de
T8.3	Evaluation/potential implementation of a open access repository	UGOE, supported by KNAW, CNRS, CSIC and KCL	Juliane Stiller stiller@fh-potsdam.de
T8.4	Organisation of joint events	PIN, supported by CLARIN, KNAW-NIOD, CNR, KCL, OEAW, MIBACT-ICCU, UGOE	Sheena Bassett sheena.giess@gmail.com

Task No.	Task	Responsibilities	Main contact
T8.5	Liaisons with other international initiatives	CLARIN, supported by PIN, INRIA, KNAW, CNR, CSIC, FORTH, KCL, OEAW, MIBACT-ICCU. Input from all partners	Bente Maegaard bmaegaard@hum.ku.dk
T8.6.	Coordination of press releases/press relations	PIN, supported by KNAW-NIOD. Input from all partners	Stefano Sbarbati stefano.sbarbati@pin.unifi.it
T8.6	Production of publicity material	KNAW-NIOD, supported by all partners.	Petra Drenth P.Drenth@niod.knaw.nl
T8.6	Production of external newsletters	KNAW-NIOD, supported by all partners.	Petra Drenth P.Drenth@niod.knaw.nl
T8.6	Production of internal newsletter	PIN, supported by all partners	Sheena Bassett sheena.giess@gmail.com
	Publicising project within partners' countries /networks. Adapting/ translating dissemination material as required	All partners	
	Disseminating project background and results at external national/ international conferences and other events	All partners. Co-ordination by KNAW-NIOD with the support of PIN.	Reto Speck reto.speck@kcl.ac.uk
	Dissemination of project's results via scientific publications	All partners. Co-ordination by KNAW-NIOD with the support of PIN	Reto Speck reto.speck@kcl.ac.uk

Table 3: Tasks and responsibilities

7.3 Resources available via associated projects

Apart from the communication and dissemination resources available via consortium partners, PARTHENOS is associated to five major European integrating/infrastructure projects and includes the two ERICs in the field of humanities research:

Name of project	Represented in PARTHENOS via (coordinator in bold)	Contact for communication
CLARIN	CLARIN-ERIC	tbc.
DARIAH*	INRIA, KNAW, CNR, CNRS, OEAW, UGOE, AA	Jakob Epler
ARIADNE	PIN , KNAW, CNR, CSIC, FORTH, OEAW, MIBACT- ICCU	Sheena Bassett
CENDARI	TCD , INRIA, KCL, UGOE, SISMEL	Catherine O'Brien
CHARISMA/IPERION-CH	CNR , CNRS, CSIC, FORTH	Emilio Cano
EHRI	KNAW , KCL, UGOE	Petra Drenth
DCH-RP	MIBACT-ICCU	Sara di Giorgio

Table 4: Associated projects

***DARIAH-ERIC is set to become a full PARTHENOS partner.**

In order to reach all the subject communities with which PARTHENOS wishes to engage and in order to achieve synergies across European RIs, it will be crucial to exploit communication and dissemination opportunities and networks available via these projects, and to carefully co-ordinate activities.

As a first step towards achieving a coordinated approach to communication/dissemination across these projects, WP8 is currently setting up an informal network of communication officers working at associated projects. This network will facilitate the exchange of information, ensure wide dissemination of relevant information across the communities addressed by these projects, and achieve synergies by avoiding duplication of effort and the sharing of resources.

For PARTHENOS, Petra Drenth (KNAW-NIOD) is responsible for initiating and managing the network. A more detailed account of its purpose, plans and operation will be provided in the next update of the communication plan (due M15).

7.4 Resources available via related international initiatives

As part of its mission, WP8 will identify and exploit connections PARTHENOS' partners have with other relevant international committees, initiatives, projects and other important research infrastructures in and beyond Europe. This work is undertaken in task T8.5 and is coordinated by Bente Maegaard (CLARIN).

We will report details about such existing connections and possible strategies of how we could make use of these for the purposes of disseminating PARTHENOS in the next update of this communication plan (due M15).

8 Communication channels

Apart from re-using existing communication and dissemination resources available at partner institutions, associated projects and related international initiatives, PARTHENOS develops, hosts and manages an array of project dissemination channels. The following section will introduce and describe each such channel and include a plan for its further development over the next 12 months.

8.1 Website

The project website – <http://www.PARTHENOS-project.eu> – is a central pillar in our communication and dissemination strategy. It is a hub for all the information about the project and its activities, events and services, and constitutes an important source of information for all stakeholder communities the project is seeking to reach. Apart from directly hosting a wealth of content, it will also contain links to relevant information available elsewhere such as publications, presentations, etc. As such it offers stakeholder one-stop access to information about the project's background, ambition and results.

The website is built using a well-known, modular web content manager (Wordpress), The website is fully responsive, meaning that it can be easily accessed and browsed via all commonly used devices (desktops, laptops, tablet and smartphones). A Google Analytics snippet is coded into the website, enabling us to generate comprehensive site usage statistics.

The design of the website facilitates the modular and multilevel communication approach defined in the previous sections. It comes with a modern and appealing layout, chosen to attract non-academic and first time users to the website, and welcome them to the European Research Infrastructures universe. Overall, the website was designed in such a way to conform to the communication principles articulated across this document:

- Clearly recognisable appearance (in line with project's visual identity)
- Appealing layout and high accessibility
- Modularity and easy adaptation to project's needs

The website will be embedded in a wider ecosystem of social media. By means of the use of multimedia products such as videos, documentaries and features narrating PARTHENOS' progress, the project aims to generate interest among youngsters and students, traditionally the groups with the highest social networks' usage penetration. While crafting this strategy, PARTHENOS fully endorses EC's vision:

"[...] communication about European research projects should aim to demonstrate the ways in which research and innovation is contributing to a European 'Innovation Union' and account for public spending by providing tangible proof that collaborative research adds value [...]"³

Needless to say, aiming to reach the wider public does not mean forgetting our core audiences. We expect to reach all of our stakeholder communities through social media and it is likely that many individuals from the professional and research communities will first encounter PARTHENOS through popular social media channels such as Twitter or YouTube.

Figure 4 gives details of the website's current structure, while Figure 5 presents a screenshot of a page.

³ European Commission (2014), Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants v1, p.1

□

Figure 4 Website structure

PARTHENOS

Fostering Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research: Networking, Organization and Synergies

ABOUT NEWS EVENTS FEATURES PRESS AREA RESOURCES

Twitter feed

Tweets Follow

@Parthenos_EU @Parthenos_EU 19h
PARTHENOS newsletter is out - eepurl.com/bp66zj

@Parthenos_EU @Parthenos_EU 23h
PARTHENOS and IperionCh showcased: youtu.be/ePQjSln7ENM?tramite @YouTube

@Parthenos_EU @Parthenos_EU 6 Jul
National news agency @Adnkronos talking about @Parthenos_EU! twitter.com/VAST_LAB/status...

@Parthenos_EU @Parthenos_EU 3 Jul
Last but not least, Reto Speck will now introduce parthenos vision for our communication activities. @EHRproject

Latest news

PARTHENOS AND IPERIONCH ON AIR

The Italian news agency Adnkronos aired this video interview of Franco Niccolucci, PARTHENOS' coordinator and Luca Pezzati, the coordinator of the project Iperion CH. The report, which

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Stefano Sbarbati

PICTURES FROM THE KICK OFF

Some pictures from the Kick off meeting

A gallery from the PARTHENOS kick off meeting, held in Palazzo Vecchio on the 3 July 2015

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PARTHENOS

PARTHENOS IN A NUTSHELL - VIDEO

Franco Niccolucci, interviewed by an Italian journalist during the kick off meeting last 3rd July, was asked to explain what the project is about in

CONTINUE READING

Stefano Sbarbati

Figure 5 Website screenshot

The website has been designed and built by PIN with the involvement of KNAW-NIOD, and it has been online since month 2 of the project.

The goals for the next 12 months are first of foremost to gradually expand the content that is available via the website. This will entail adding more concise background and contextual information about the project, for instance through a series of FAQ-style questions and answers about PARTHENOS and the context in which it operates. Likewise, news about PARTHENOS events, announcements, or about significant activities

happening in associated projects, will be added on a continuous basis. As the project develops over time, we will also regularly publish news stories about the project's progress and its substantial results.

Furthermore, we will continuously extend and adapt the design, structure and functionality of the site in response to feedback and changing requirements.

PIN takes the lead in developing and expanding the website with substantive editorial input provided by KNAW-NIOD. Feedback on the site, and input for new content will be sought from all PARTHENOS partners.

8.2 Social networks

PARTHENOS takes full advantage of the most used and effective social networks to support its dissemination. We will thereby aim at taking full advantage of the extensive social networks that are already in existence within the consortium.

A Twitter (@PARTHENOS_EU) account has been setup, and will be used to report on the project's activities, and alert followers to new content on the website. During major events (such as the kick off meetings, participation in conferences etc.) KNAW-NIOD and PIN will facilitate live blogging sessions.

A Youtube channel has also been setup (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCnKJnFoIFfoAl3VH51t1hw>). The channel already showcases two videos, and we plan to produce further short videos to document forthcoming PARTHENOS meetings and events.

Flickr will be used to share the project's photographic documentation. The official PARTHENOS page is available at https://www.flickr.com/photos/parthenos_eu/.

Usage of further social networks such as Google+, LinkedIn and Facebook will be considered when and if the need arises.

Over the next 12 months, our main goal is to significantly expand our social networks, and to ensure that our followers receive frequent, interesting and engaging updates from the project.

PIN and KNAW-NIOD share responsibility for managing the project's social media accounts. All partners are encouraged to help widen PARTHENOS' social networks by following us on, retweeting, etc.

8.3 Mailing list

Website visitors can sign-up to a PARTHENOS email-list. This mailing list is hosted on the popular Mailchimp platform (see <http://mailchimp.com/>). Subscribers to the list will receive regular email updates and news about PARTHENOS to their inboxes by means of regular newsletters (c.f. section 8.4).

Our goal over the next 12 months is to populate our mailing list. During the first two months, we will focus on gathering the details of individuals working at PARTHENOS partner institutions. Partner recipient of the newsletter will be encouraged to spread the PARTHENOS Newsletter among their own networks, which is expected to gradually result in a substantial number of subscribers from outside the PARTHENOS consortium.

PIN and KNAW-NIOD manage the PARTHENOS mailing list. All partners will contribute to its population (forwarding of newsletters, spreading the word, etc.)

8.4 Newsletters

We plan to keep the subscribers to our email-list up-to-date about PARTHENOS by means of a periodic Newsletter (ca. 4 issues per year).

The Newsletters will provide subscribers with a concise summary of all the latest PARTHENOS-related news since the last issue. Apart from reports about the project's progress and announcements about forthcoming events, etc., the newsletter will also contain news about important developments in the various fields related to PARTHENOS' activities.

A template for the newsletter has been designed by PIN in accordance with PARTHENOS' visual style – see below.

As already mentioned above, we will aim to produce 4 issues of the newsletter over the forthcoming 12 months, with the first issue distributed on 20 July 2015.

The newsletter will be edited by KNAW-NIOD and PIN, but will contain contributions from all partners and all work packages.

Figure 6: Newsletter

8.5 E-journal and open access repository

WP8 will evaluate the need for creating a scientific e-journal covering the field of e-humanities research. It will further investigate the possibility of setting-up and managing a scientific repository service for open access pre-print storage of scientific papers

Over the forthcoming 12 months, we will investigate the community requirements and needs for an e-journal and repository in conjunction with WP2. UGOE⁴ is leading this activity, supported by KNAW, CNRS, CSIC and KCL.

8.6 (Joint-) events

PARTHENOS will implement a comprehensive programme of joint events (symposia, workshops, public presentations) either directly managed by the project, or co-organised and with other relevant international/national initiatives.

Over the forthcoming 12 months, we will identify themes for events, possible co-organisers and suitable venues. We will also plan fully at least one joint-event in that period, to take place in the first half of 2016.

Contacts are already established with the many research communities composing PARTHENOS; among the others, PIN is exploring the possibility to hold one event during the DARIAH and CLARIN general assemblies.

PIN is leading this activity, supported by CLARIN, KNAW-NIOD, CNR, KCL, OEAW, MIBACT-ICCU, UGOE.

⁴ It is expected that the University of Potsdam will take over all of the University of Göttingen's (UGOE) contributions to PARTHENOS.

9 Dissemination materials

To support the project’s communication and dissemination mission, an initial set of dissemination materials has been produced. These materials, as well as our plans for the creation of further materials, are presented in this section.

9.1 Logo and visual style

A distinct, clear and easily recognizable visual style is arguably as important to the achievement of our communication and dissemination goals, as are availability of suitable dissemination channels and concise tailored messages. Indeed, as famously coined by Marshall McLuhan, “The medium is the message”.

One of the main goals in designing the project identity was to represent a key assumption behind PARTHENOS, namely the importance of digital technologies in the fields of Linguistic Studies, Digital Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology and other related fields. Therefore, the project’s visual identity has to symbolize the bridge between technologies on the one hand and the above mentioned research fields on the other.

This bridge is most prominently visible in the project’s logo which seeks to symbolize the linkages between heritage and modernity. It is composed of two main circles, the outer recalling the antiquity and the inner representing the modernity through an abstraction of modern electronics wiring, rendered according to the circularity of the logotype.

**Figure 6 PARTHENOS
logo (simple)**

PARTHENOS

Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking.
Optimization and Synergies

Figure 8 PARTHENOS Logo (w/ description)

A clear, minimalistic approach informs all of the documentation templates created for the project. So far the following resources have been created (all available via D4Science):

- Logo (in various versions)
- Letterhead
- PowerPoint template
- Word deliverable template
- A visual style guide including details about font usage and colour schemes
- A rollup used during the kick-off meeting

9.2 Press relations

Obtaining good press coverage is one of the long term goals of PARTHENOS. Good press about the project's activities means stronger and more sustainable impact for the project. It is, therefore, crucial to set up effective and coherent guidelines to be followed by all the partners when dealing with PARTHENOS press releases.

An up-to-date information media kit and project press releases will be developed by PIN and KNAW-NIOD for all the project's major events and to disseminate the project results. Partners will be responsible for translations and regional adaptations as well as for spreading the press releases to relevant regional stakeholders and at European/international level.

Partners wishing to schedule national or international press conferences related to PARTHENOS will need to discuss in advance the feasibility. The primary contact for all press relations is Stefano Sbarbati (PIN). As a rule of thumb, press conferences are to be scheduled only to present to the press relevant and news worthy project outcomes.

This rule is valid both for the international media and the local press. Each partner is responsible for the organization of press conference and especially inviting relevant journalists.

KNAW-NIOD and PIN will support these activities concerning press conferences with material if needed. Depending upon the type of news, there might be the need to include some additional material to the press release – such as fact sheets, background information and photos in high definition. A press release template has been created and can be accessed on D4Science (<https://goo.gl/KnXUTV>).

9.3 Media productions

Thanks to the expertise provided by the consortium, PARTHENOS communication will be also based on enriched media. Events, topics and project's update will be covered with videos and short documentaries, in order to appeal to wider audiences. The use of videos and enriched media represents not only a means to directly reach wider audiences and communities, but is also a useful instrument for granting access to PARTHENOS to online press and television interested in covering the topic.

The production of a series of videos covering the major issues tackled by PARTHENOS is currently under discussions, and its feasibility will be discussed in the next iteration of the present document.

9.4 Further planned dissemination materials

KNAW-NIODS is currently is currently preparing a first version of a generic PARTHENOS PowerPoint presentation and a project leaflet. Both will be ready in autumn 2015, and will focus on a general presentation of the project and its main activities. They will be made available to all partners for usage and distribution at conferences and other suitable events. At a later stage in the project, an updated PowerPoint presentation and a more detailed brochure will be prepared.

10 External dissemination activities for Year 1

Section 9 above already contains details about our plans for the first year in regard to the dissemination and communication channels directly managed by PARTHENOS. This section contains details about potential dissemination avenues outside the direct control of the project.

10.1 Events

Active participation at external events (conferences, workshops, symposia, fairs) is crucial to PARTHENOS' dissemination strategy as it allows direct contact with the research communities with which the project wishes to engage.

All partners will present PARTHENOS at external events with KNAW-NIOD providing coordination.

Table 5 below details suitable events pertaining to fields of Linguistic studies, digital humanities, archaeology, cultural heritage and history that could be fruitfully targeted by PARTHENOS. It should be noted that for some of the earlier events, deadlines for calls of papers and registration will already have passed. They are listed here for reference purposes in order to identify future iterations of the same events.

Name of event	Location	Date	Community
8th Corpus Linguistics Conference (CL2015)	Lancaster, UK	21-24 Jul 2015	Linguistics
11th IEEE International Conference on e-Science	Munich, Germany	31 Aug - 4 Sep 2015	Research Infrastructure (RI)
Digital Heritage International Congress 2015	Granada, Spain	28 Sep-2 Oct 2015	Heritage
21st Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA 2015)	Glasgow, UK	2-6 Sep 2015	Archaeology
Semantic Web for Cultural Heritage workshop (SW4CH'15)	Poitiers, France	8-11 Sep 2015	Cultural Heritage
International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL)	Poznan, Poland	14-18 Sep 2015	RI
2 nd International Symposium on Virtual Archaeology, Museums and Cultural Tourism 2015	Delphi, Greece	23-26 Sep 2015	Archaeology; Cultural Heritage
2nd International APEX conference (*)	Budapest, Hungary	7-9 Sep 2015	RI, History
National Movements and Intermediary Structures in Europe (NISE) Annual Gathering (*)	Swansea, UK	1-3 Sep 2015	RI; History
Athena Plus Conference	Rome, Italy	21 Oct 2015	Cultural Heritage; RI
Europeana Digital Service Infrastructure meeting (DSI)	Rome, Italy	23 Oct 2015	Cultural Heritage; RI
ICDH 2015: XII International Conference on Digital Heritage	London, UK	27-28 Nov 2015	Cultural Heritage
Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies (CHNT), Computer Applications & Quantitative Methods in Archaeology (CAA) Conference 2016	Vienna, Austria	2-4 Nov 2015	Cultural Heritage
Oslo, Norway	Oslo, Norway	28 Mar-1 Apr 2016	Archaeology
Language Resources and Evaluation Conference (LREC) 2016	Portoroz, Slovenia	23-28 May 2016	Linguistics
Digital Humanities 2016	Krakow, Poland	10-16 Jul 2016	Digital Humanities
22th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists (EAA2016)	Vilnius, Lithuania	30 Aug-4 Sep 2016	Archaeology
17th European Association for Lexicography (EURALEX) Conference	Tbilisi, Georgia	6-10 Sep 2016	Linguistics
8th Plenary Meeting of Research Data Alliance	United States	11-16 Sep 2015	RI
iPRES 2016, 13 th International Conference on Digital Preservation	Bern, Switzerland	3-7 Oct 2016	RI
9th Plenary Meeting of Research Data Alliance	Barcelona, Spain	9 Mar 2017	RI
EAA 2017 23 rd Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists	Maastricht, Netherlands	3 Sep 2017	Archaeology

Table 5: External events

(*) PARTHENOS already has a confirmed participation at these events

In addition to such external events, the two ERICs participating in PARTHENOS and associated RI projects, will periodically host their own events which provide excellent dissemination opportunities for PARTHENOS. Table 6 below provides an overview of such forthcoming events.

<i>Name of event</i>	<i>Location</i>	<i>Date</i>
CLARIN workshop on digital resources and services in social sciences and in humanities	Prague, Czech Republic	24 Sep 2015
CLARIN Annual Conference	Wroclaw, Poland	15-17 Oct 2015
DARIAH General Assembly	Berlin, Germany	1 Nov 2015

Table 6: Events organised by associated ERICs/projects

10.2 International event co-operations

PARTHENOS is promoting the organization of workshops with top-level extra-EU institutions and research communities, planned for early 2016. Among the others, the discussion is ongoing with the Library of Congress (US), the National Gallery of Art (US), a group of US Universities, the Mexican Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia (INAH), the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM) and other institutions in North America.

The aim is to foster the collaboration with world-class institutions in the fields addressed by PARTHENOS, in order to exchange best-practices and strengthen PARTHENOS' output effectiveness.

10.3 Publications

PARTHENOS will be publishing its substantive research writings in academic journals. All partners are encouraged to publish their work in academic journals. Authors of scientific publications should adhere to standard good academic practice, and particularly note the following:

- Mention EU support for the work,
- Notify the consortium of the publication,
- Take cognizance of the EC's Open Access Policy,

- Provide a digital copy to the consortium, to be made available on the website (if the publisher agrees with the Open Access Self-Archiving). If not, a link will be provided to an archive copy elsewhere, or a copy will be kept in storage in case self-archiving is not allowed.

Table 7 below provides a first overview of potential journals that partners could target with their articles. It should be noted that this list is currently very incomplete, and will be updated as an outcome of task 8.3. As it is expected that publication of scientific papers will predominantly occur in the second half of the project, a more extent version of possible publication outlets will be provided in the next iteration of this deliverable.

Name of journal	Deadlines
International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing	<p>The <i>International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing</i> (formerly <i>History and Computing</i>) is one of the world's premier multi-disciplinary, peer-reviewed forums for research on all aspects of arts and humanities computing. It focuses both on conceptual or theoretical approaches and case studies or essays demonstrating how advanced information technologies further scholarly understanding of traditional topics in the arts and humanities. The journal also welcomes submissions on policy, epistemological, and pedagogical issues insofar as they relate directly to computing-based arts and humanities research.</p> <p>http://www.eupublishing.com/journal/ijhac</p>
Digital Humanities Quarterly	<p><i>Digital Humanities Quarterly</i> (DHQ) is published by the Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (ADHO). It is an open-access, peer-reviewed, digital journal covering all aspects of digital media in the humanities.</p> <p>http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/about/about.html</p>
Digital Scholarship in the Humanities (DSH)	<p>Formerly known as LLC (Literary & Linguistic Computing), DSH is an international peer reviewed journal on digital scholarship in the humanities, published by Oxford Journals on behalf of the Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations. It publishes results of research projects, description and evaluation of techniques and methodologies, reports on work in progress.</p>

Journal of Computing and Cultural Heritage	JOCCH publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to innovative use of information and communication technologies in support of Cultural Heritage http://jocch.acm.org
International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Area	IJHDR is a quarterly peer-reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage and Digital Libraries

Table 7: Journals

11 Communication evaluation and assessment

The effectiveness of PARTHENOS' communication and evaluation activities will be periodically measured. Each subsequent iteration of this deliverable will provide an assessment of the implementation of the previous plan, and provide targets for the forthcoming period. Periodic evaluation is undertaken to guarantee that all our stakeholder communities are reached and provided with appropriate information. It also has an important to play in shaping future iterations of the communication plan by providing feedback on what works and what needs refinement.

All partners have a significant role to play, not only in the implementation of the communication plan, but also in its iterative formulation and review. In particular, all partners are called upon to update their own dissemination activities according to the survey template described in Section 7.1 previously.

For the first period, spanning months 1-15, the following targets are proposed:

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Quantity (by month 15)</i>
Avg. number of website visitors per month	200
Total number of website visitors	1,000
Number of EU/EEA countries reached through website	25
Total number of referrals	200
Number of contacts in the mailing list	150
Number of twitter followers	100
Avg. monthly number of tweet impressions	800
Number of joint events	0-1
Number of attendees at joint events	0-50
Number of press releases	3
Number of leaflets/other publicity materials distributed	300
Number of conference papers	6
Number of attendees reached at conferences	150
Number of scientific papers	0
Articles in professional journals and online newsletters	3

Table 8: Performance targets